

Alkali Metal Complexes : Homobinuclear Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with *Bis*-(8-Hydroxy-5-quinolyl)methane

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A number of homobinuclear complexes, having the general formula $(ML)_2 \cdot H_2L'$, where $M = Li, Na$ or K ; $L =$ deprotonated organic acid (anthranilic or salicylic), *o*-nitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid or 8-hydroxyquinoline; and $H_2L' = bis$ -(8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)methane, have been obtained. All the complexes are characteristically coloured.

The ir spectra of the products point to the presence of hydrogen bonding which may be one of the dominant factors for their stabilisation. The analytical data suggest a coordination number four for the alkali metals. Thermal, ir and solution studies reveal that these adducts are genuine complexes.

IN continuation to our previous work¹, we examined the title ligand for complex formation with alkali metal salts of some organic acids.

Complex formation was favoured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide having low dielectric constant and in presence of excess of the ligand. Otherwise in a high dielectric medium ions would be more stabilised in solution² due to their high electrostatic energy and would thus minimise the chance of complex formation.

The general formula of the homobinuclear complexes is $(ML)_2 \cdot H_2L'$, where $M = Li, Na$ or K ; $L =$ deprotonated organic acid (anthranilic or salicylic), *o*-nitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid or 8-hydroxyquinoline; and $H_2L' = bis$ -(8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)methane.

Experimental

The ligand H_2L' was prepared by the method of Horowitz and Perrors³. It was characterised by elemental analyses, melting point and ir spectra (nujol/hexachlorobutadiene).

ML and H_2L' (2:1) was refluxed in *N,N*-dimethylformamide for 4-6 h at 120° while stirring. On addition of solvent ether to the cooled reaction mixture (except for the adducts of alkali metal anthranilates where chloroform was used), the separated adduct was filtered, washed with ether (or chloroform for anthranilates) and dried at 120°. H_2L' adducts of anthranilates were converted into a sticky mass on addition of ether. A cream coloured precipitate

separated during the reaction between H_2L' and salicylates. Solvent ether was used only for washing the precipitate. Adducts with alkali metal oxinates were separated similarly.

Molar conductivity was measured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (0.001 *M*) at 23° using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter, Type 303.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable in air under dry conditions, but are hygroscopic otherwise and need to be stored on anhydrous $CaCl_2$. Complexes of anthranilates, *o*-nitrophenolates, 1-nitroso-2-naphtholates and 2-hydroxy-3-naphtholates are soluble in DMF, whereas others are partly soluble in DMF or *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone. All the complexes are insoluble in nonpolar solvents such as chloroform, *n*-hexane, benzene, toluene and diethylether. Selected physico-chemical properties and analytical data of the ligand and its complexes are listed in Table 1.

No conclusion can be drawn from the thermal behaviour of the complexes which decompose at a temperature detectably lower than the melting point of H_2L' .

Ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes indicate that the latter are not the physical mixtures of ML and H_2L' .

The ir spectra of the ligand H_2L' and its coordination compounds with various bivalent transition metals have been reported³ and it was found that these are polymeric in nature. The spectra of these

TABLE-1

Compound	Colour	Decomp. temp.	Conductivity $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	M
$\text{H}_2\text{L}'$	Colourless	280	—	75.80 (75.50)	4.80 (4.64)	9.25 (9.26)	—
$(\text{LiAnc})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^a$	Red	225	0.5	68.65 (68.51)	2.85 (2.77)	9.85 (9.69)	—
$(\text{NaAnc})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^a$	Red	180	0.5	65.24 (64.92)	2.89 (2.62)	8.83 (9.18)	7.80 (7.54)
$(\text{KAnc})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Red	195	6.0	62.00 (61.68)	2.85 (2.49)	8.78 (8.72)	12.05 (12.15)
$(\text{LiSalA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Cream	265	—	67.00 (67.12)	4.25 (4.06)	4.70 (4.74)	—
$(\text{NaSalA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Cream	240	—	64.26 (63.66)	3.95 (3.86)	4.50 (4.50)	7.80 (7.89)
$(\text{KSalA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Cream	255	—	60.80 (60.55)	3.87 (3.67)	4.25 (4.28)	11.85 (11.92)
$(\text{NaONP})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Brown	230	2.5	60.24 (59.61)	3.65 (3.58)	8.80 (8.97)	7.35 (7.37)
$(\text{KONP})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Brown	250	8.5	56.85 (56.71)	3.56 (3.86)	8.50 (8.54)	11.95 (11.89)
$(\text{Li1N2N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Yellowish brown	240	2.0	70.90 (70.90)	3.99 (3.94)	8.40 (8.48)	—
$(\text{Na1N2N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Black	225	2.6	62.25 (62.68)	3.80 (3.76)	8.46 (8.09)	6.68 (6.66)
$(\text{K1N2N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Deep brown	140	6.0	64.85 (64.64)	3.78 (3.89)	7.78 (7.78)	10.80 (10.77)
$(\text{Li2H3NA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Grey	225	1.8	71.56 (71.51)	3.85 (3.78)	4.18 (4.07)	—
$(\text{Na2H3NA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Pale brown	210	1.8	68.45 (68.39)	3.89 (3.61)	3.88 (3.89)	6.40 (6.39)
$(\text{K2H3NA})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^b$	Pale brown	295	5.0	65.00 (65.42)	3.54 (3.46)	3.70 (3.72)	10.08 (10.37)
$(\text{Li8HQ})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Greyish blue	265	—	78.50 (73.51)	4.54 (4.30)	9.15 (9.27)	—
$(\text{Na8HQ})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Greenish blue	260	—	70.00 (69.81)	4.00 (4.09)	8.80 (8.80)	7.50 (7.23)
$(\text{K8HQ})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}'^c$	Deep blue	210	—	66.80 (66.46)	4.05 (3.89)	7.40 (8.98)	11.50 (11.67)

a= Adduct obtained on addition of chloroform.
 b= Adduct obtained on addition of ether.
 c= Adduct separated during reaction.

polymers indicate that their peak frequencies are very similar.

The bands assigned^{3,4} for $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$ are 3335 (OH), 1580 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) and 1420 cm^{-1} (OH). The 3335 cm^{-1} band disappears on complexation and is distinguishable for the ν_{NH} (3420–3380 and 3320–3270) of anthranilates. The 1580 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) has split bands at 1575–1565 cm^{-1} and 1605–1590 cm^{-1} suggesting the coordination of the $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ group of the quinoline ring with the cation. The shifting of 1420 cm^{-1} band to poorly resolved band at 1415–1400 cm^{-1} confirms chelation of the hydroxyl oxygen.

A new broad band of weak to medium intensity at 2400–1800 cm^{-1} is exhibited by all the complexes suggesting $\text{O}-\text{H} \cdots \text{O}/\text{N} \cdots \text{H}-\text{O}$ bonding which may be the main force that holds $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$ with ML.

Since molar conductivities of a 1 : 1 electrolyte⁵ are 35–40 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ while that of a non-electrolyte around zero, each product (Table 1) is

practically a “non-electrolyte” because of a strong pairing of the acid anion with the concerned cation. Measurements could not be made for the insoluble products of salicylates and 8-hydroxyquinolates.

The probable general structure of the products is

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